

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LINGUOSTYLISTIC MEANS OF CREATING AN IMAGE

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Abstract

The paper deals with the linguistic aspect of a film title. It examines the role and functions of the title. It also analyses the models of mass communication, their productivity. The paper makes references to the history of development film industry in the context of a film title evolution.

Keywords: film industry, film title, means of expressiveness, nominativity, semantic nature, paratext.

The role of the film industry plays a big role in popular culture these days. Every year, many films are released worldwide, their main task is to convey the author's unique point of view, which he reveals by demonstrating the experiences or exposing a social problem. Films should attract the viewer with the opportunity to have fun or gain some new knowledge in a particular area, as well as inspire the audience. Watching foreign films, the viewer gets the opportunity to learn something new about another ethnic group and the countries in which they live, trace their culture and understand the mentality of these nationalities or races.

In our opinion, the title plays one of the main roles in understanding of the film. It is also important to understand the information embedded in the film, such interaction with the viewer is possible only with the correct translation of the title of the film. Therefore, we can conclude that the translator should be as focused as possible when translating the film title. [1]

What is the film title supposed to reflect? The most important feature that the title should reveal the individuality of the film, which contributes to the promotion of the film among other works. The titles no longer contain dry theses. These "privileges" were left to the press. Turning to the review of film titles, we would like to remind that most of the texts of the Middle Ages were named after the main character or contained his name in the title. The title could also reflect its content. There were also cases where titles were assigned later as a simple text identifier. We can say that the titles of books began to appear more as a sales tool. But the very concept of "headline" appeared around the dawn of the 1550s, when new means of communication were born (leaflets with religious propaganda, brief essays on incidents and disasters) - all that we can get these days using the media. It was during this period of time that the concept of the headline was born, which should convey to the listener, viewer and reader the main idea contained in the text. Because of this, such a phenomenon as headlines appeared, which were supposed to "speak" for themselves and give a complete picture of themselves. The importance of the headlines increased when the press moved to periodicals and the original text was changed. So, in comparison with the initial stage, the role of headings has increased, because the separation of information has become more convenient

and there are more and more subheadings. Jean Pierre Ségun noted in his essay that the titles of the books were simple and concise annotations. [2]

Because of the new organization, the use of headings has become a mandatory item in translation activities. At this time, lists of actors also appeared, which were presented in the form of maps and photographs, and after which they were included in the film. Such images showed the replicas of the actors, we can say that these were subtitles, but a more extended version. As cinema developed, titles began to be added, but only after the advent of sound in cinema. The titles began to function as a transition, they also began to show the name of the director and introduced a hierarchy of actors. During this period, the titles of films ceased to be kept within the framework of pragmatic communication and began to turn into plots that set the mood, as well as the visual character of the film.

The next aspect that we would like to highlight is the model of mass communication. Over the years, the titles of films have changed, mainly influenced by the way the film was processed and the analysis of the audio sequence. As a result, three different models of communication have emerged:

1) editorial - this is the production of individual items (text materials, books, disks and film media), which are sold as separate items. It is worth noting that they all have a long service life.

2) written - this type of model implies periodic and regular publication (newspapers and magazines). Each new release makes the previous one obsolete. [3]

3) streaming - characterized by a certain timing (transmissions on television and radio). As in the previous paragraph, the product of this model becomes obsolete after the release of a new one.

It is worth noting that for each such model there corresponds a certain plan from the economic side, as well as an organized distribution of responsibilities. Often, the productivity of these models is increased by a combination of several, for example: the distribution of film production on television or the serial publication of books. It is worth clarifying that the streaming model appeared only in 1920, and the rest originate in the first half of the 17th century. According to John Ellis, one can understand that these models were slowly formed within the framework of an unstructured market, and

only at the beginning of the 19th century did the models begin to overlap with each other. Each of these systems found its echo in the creation of headings and subheadings. An innovation of the time was the use of headlines in newspapers.

By the end of the 19th century, the film industry was already rapidly gaining momentum, and already in 1895 two models were distinguished by analogy: the editorial model and the informational one. But these days, we don't share our idea of a film as a piece of work. Consequently, we can conclude that the title of the film may look like the title of a book (many films are based on novels and bear their names). But in those years, it was never known what the title of the film would be and how it would be distributed.

What is a movie title? The title of a film is a parent text, which means one or more texts, not including the main text. Finn Frandsen argued that the paratext should include such concepts as: title, notes, attribution, abstract and title. Film production and paratext use different media. In cinema, the paratext can be reduced to the simplest expressions, but on television, the importance of linguistic and visual paratext is growing due to great competition. The viewer, the reader must go through the primal text only in order to understand the idea correctly. But often this theory is not confirmed, and the viewer is not very interested in the original text, and when he sees it on the screen, he usually switches the channel. [4]

Nowadays, film production is one of the largest entertainment industries; every day millions of viewers watch multiple television series and other television projects. It is worth noting that when broadcast on television, the film retains its original title and does not change it with each series. John Ellis noted that There is a bad way of arranging movie titles when the title uses a noun and an associated index, a scheme commonly used in talk show and entertainment programming. The streaming model assumes that no one will remember the content after the movie has been broadcast.

Now I would like to consider the functions of movie titles. Dirk Delabasti said: "The main function is to define. Without the initial identification, we would not be able to talk about the film, promotion would be impossible, and analysis of the film would be impossible. If a text comes to us without a title, we must give it a title in order to talk about it. So you can draw an analogy with computer files, where if the file already exists, it gets the same name, but with a serial number. It should be borne in mind that nominativity is the most obvious function of the name, it is worth highlighting the other functions:

- The title guides us through the flow of media information.
- The title is a means of interpreting the text, shows a certain point of view and briefly summarizes the film.
- The main function of the name of a film production can be its promotion, in which case the name should be easy to remember.

It can be assumed that the titles of the films should be different from the title of the novel or drama, but,

unfortunately, there are a small number of original film titles. In his work, Dirk Delabastia described the fact that the combination of different media or channels of communication in one text does not have any meaning. Therefore, more

number of movie titles will be able to work as novel titles and vice versa.

The work on the translation of the title of the film is very interesting, it can be viewed from different angles: the audience receives a huge number of translated works in various forms of translations, which have been previously reported. Multiple observations lead us to the conclusion that the titles of modern film production often appear in a bilingual version.

Working on the translation of movie titles shows us a concrete analysis of the object. The main thing in the work of a translator is to trace the adequacy of the title of the translated and the original.

The next method of translation of the name can be distinguished - the adaptive method of translation, i.e. we return to the original source, with such a translation the translated name corresponds to the name of the source. Therefore, we can conclude that when analyzing the translations of titles into Russian, we have different options, as the translation work makes us understand that translations of titles often use already fixed adaptation strategies.

It is worth noting that the translation of film titles is referred to as the translation of fiction. I would like to highlight the main transformations that are used in the translation of texts, they can also be applied to the translation of film titles.

Interlingual transformations - the transition from the lexical unit of the original to the units of translation. Such changes are formal-semantic in nature.

These techniques can be considered not only as a means of analyzing the dependencies between the dictionary equivalents of a foreign language and their counterparts in the translated language. Depending on the initial composition of the name, translation transformations are divided into lexical and grammatical, while both of these aspects are considered as a whole or passing from one to another.

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